

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF PREPARING TEENAGERS FOR FAMILY LIFE DURING EDUCATION

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Today, 62% of the population of Uzbekistan are children and teenagers, that is, young men and women under 30 years of age, and a certain part of them are young families. Young families are important subjects of socialpolitical, economic, cultural-spiritual renewal and development of society, and play an important role in influencing the complex processes taking place in social life and driving development. plays Therefore, at present, a deep and comprehensive analysis of the formation and development of the spiritual, moral and spiritual world of young families is of great importance from a scientific and practical point of view. From this point of view, the formation of strong families, social protection of motherhood and childhood, creation of favorable conditions for the birth of physically healthy and mentally strong children in families, and effective family education in the process of establishing a strong relationship between families and the public issues of creating cooperation are being paid attention at the level of state policy. In February 1993, the establishment of the Order of "Healthy Generation" and the adoption of the State Program "Healthy Generation" are a clear proof of our opinion.

The concept of maturity for marriage, in turn, is a very complex and relative concept. Because a person is a creature that is constantly developing and improving, regularly reaching new heights in professional activity or spiritual and moral development. If we talk about the "full maturity" of a person in this or that activity, it means that he has reached a certain limit and cannot develop further. That is why when talking about a person's maturity for marriage or any activity, the concept of "maturity" cannot be appropriate in a narrow sense. That is why, when talking about the "maturity" of a person, especially "maturity" for marriage and family life, this concept is a certain generally accepted standard, an average norm, a certain conditional "unit of measurement". used only as pointers and the like. For example, for all educational institutions (schools, high schools, colleges, institutes) there will be graduation exams (system of state exams, thesis defense systems, etc.) it will be possible to determine the index. This gives them a certain right that they can continue their education later or work in a certain specialty. From this point of view, "maturity" serves as an

indicator that determines the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of reaching a certain stage, phase, limit of development with a certain accuracy. The issue of a person's readiness for marriage and family life is a very complex indicator that has an individual character that cannot be measured by any strict standards. All of the above shows that pre-marital factors are usually complex problems. In the psychological literature dedicated to the social and psychological problems of the modern family, different forms and manifestations of premarital factors are distinguished. Below, we bring to your attention the information about some of them: Pre-marriage factors include: the maturity of the young people who are starting a family: the maturity of the family: their motives for starting a family: the period of time they have known each other before starting a family (how long they have known each other) terms and conditions : their visions of their future family life can be included. Of course, these factors may have different characteristics in different young people, while each of them, in turn, differs in several types. For example, when it is called maturity for marriage, it is possible to distinguish aspects of maturity of young people who are building a family: physical (physiological), sexual, legal, economic, spiritual-moral, psychological.

Among them, the indicators of legal and sexual maturity have sufficiently clear symptoms and signs, and there is a lot of information about them in the relevant legal, medical, and psychological literature, while the economic, moral, and psychological aspects are a little more complicated, a fixed indicator, characterized by the fact that it does not have a limit. For example, a person's sexual maturity has its own factors. According to clinical observations, sexual maturity (puberty) in modern girls is 12-14 years old, and in boys 14-16 years old. Of course, this maturity can happen earlier in some children and later in others. These indicators may differ by ± 2 years.

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